

Data Science & Big Data Analytics

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

What impact might Big Data Analytics with Machine Learning (ML) have upon Power and Utilities Company? According to one view, it's not every day we think about our energy consumption. Do you know what you paid on your last electricity bill? Or what your thermostat is set to right now? Less often, we think about how to reduce it - and even then, how to take action. But how have Utilities company been tackling these challenges.

In particular, this focuses upon Machine learning techniques and their potential impact upon Power & Utilities Company. Broadly speaking, machine learning involves computer algorithms that have the ability to “learn” or improve in performance over time on some task. Given that there are multiple Artificial Intelligence (AI) approaches, why highlight machine learning in particular? In the last few decades, researchers have successfully used machine learning to automate a variety of sophisticated tasks that were previously presumed to require human cognition. These applications range from autonomous (i.e., self-driving) cars, to automated language translation, prediction, speech recognition, and computer vision.

Researchers have also begun to apply these techniques in the context of Power & Utilities company.

What Is Machine Learning?

“Machine learning” refers to a subfield of computer science concerned with computer programs that are able to learn from experience and thus improve their performance over time. As will be discussed, the idea that the computers are “learning” is largely a

metaphor and does not imply that computers systems are artificially replicating the advanced cognitive systems thought to be involved in human learning. Rather, we can consider these algorithms to be learning in a functional sense: they are capable of changing their behavior to enhance their performance on some task through experience.

Commonly, machine learning algorithms are used to detect patterns in data in order to automate complex tasks or make predictions. Today, such algorithms are used in a variety of real-world commercial applications including Internet search results, facial recognition, fraud detection, and data mining. Machine learning is closely associated with the larger enterprise of “predictive analytics” as researchers often employ machine learning methods to analyze existing data to predict the likelihood of uncertain outcomes. If performing well, machine learning algorithms may produce automated results that approximate those that would have been made by a similarly situated person. Machine learning is thus often

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considered a branch of artificial intelligence, since a well-performing algorithm may produce automated results that appear “intelligent.”

2. Aim

To understand how machine learning application develops an "understanding" of how certain events will positively and negatively impact company's services.

3. Material and methods

A project called Genesis is to be examined. The Genesis project is RCT's business intelligence project, which will be housed in a large and complex backend system that has load balancing, replication and high availability incorporated in the architecture. The platform is based on the ELK (Elasticsearch, Logstash and Kibana) suite. Elasticsearch is a No SQL platform with search capability and is based on the lucene indexing platform. Logstash is a logs processing pipeline which is being used to push data from a number of data sources (including csv files, databases and other data storage sources).

Kibana is the visualization tool that allows users to make visual sense of the data housed in the Elasticsearch indices.

The indexing pipeline will pull data from the various databases via APIs or automated data dumps. This data will include the following:

Vending / PPM platform Billing / Post Paid platform Finance / Accounting platform SCADA backend systems SharePoint Backends KPI and Employee Performance Tracking Organisation-Wide Health and Safety Tracking Other system backends as they are on-boarded.

4. Results

1. The Search and Analytics Engine

Elasticsearch is a search platform that provides a near real time

Note:

Each Elasticsearch shard is a Lucene index. There is a maximum number of documents you can have in a single Lucene index. As of LUCENE-5843, the limit is 2,147,483,519 (= Integer.MAX_VALUE - 128) documents. You can monitor shard sizes using the `_cat/shards` api.

2. The Indexing Pipeline

The indexing pipeline provides datasets that populate the search and analytics engine.

The intention is to have an index defined for one particular datasource. However data sources shall be deployed into a single index for datasets that are similar - such billing data and vending data. In such cases it will be important to define a document structure that is compatible with the multiple datasets combined.

3. The Data Visualization Frontend System

Kibana is the frontend system being deployed to provide the data analytics visualization.

- 如何 在 虚拟机 中 安装 操作系统?

1. 虚拟机 软件 安装 操作系统

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